

The Electric Universe Memo

For Plasma, Electromagnetic, and Diffusion-Catastrophic Cosmologies (EPEMC)

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V 1.0

Physics & Chemistry

Electromagnetism (the Force)

The Force is a unified conceptualization of the entire active [force](#), directive vector, or field acting upon objects and light (it is light, and needs [no medium to propagate that we know of](#)). The Force, EM for short, acts upon different scales and has many different side-studies of unique effects and scales. The [equations for EM](#) are listed elsewhere as [Maxwell-Heaviside equations](#) or more recently as [New-EM](#) (Distinti), but are also relevant in [quantum mechanics](#) as all [particle 'masses' are measured](#) in [electronvolts](#). [Charge](#) is measured in Q (Coulombs) or as [tension](#) (V, voltage). [Flux](#) is measured in [current](#) (I, amperes) for electricity and [gauss for magnetism](#). The side studies of note are:

- [Faraday Effect](#): “the rotation of the plane of polarization of electromagnetic waves in certain substances in a magnetic field.”
- [Circuit law](#): $V=IR$; $\sum V = 0$; $N1/N2 = V1/V2$
- [Capacitance](#); storage of charge in electric fields
- [Inductance](#); storage of current in magnetic fields
- [Impedance](#) vs [Conductance](#)
- [Piezoelectricity](#); electricity related to crystal lattice deformation
- [Pyroelectricity](#): “the ability of certain materials to generate a temporary voltage when they are heated or cooled.”
- [Biophotons](#): “photons of light in the ultraviolet and low visible light range that are produced by a biological system.”
- [Superconductivity](#) $R=0$ @ or below specific temperatures for certain materials
- [Van-der-Waals forces](#) “weak, short-range electrostatic attractive forces between uncharged molecules, arising from the interaction of permanent or transient electric dipole moments.”
- [Electroweak force/interaction](#) “Although these two forces appear very different at everyday low energies, the theory models them as two different aspects of the same force.”
- [Strong \(Atomic\) force](#); in [Structured Atomic Model](#) the short bond of protons to electrons inside the nucleus due to a thousand fold+ increase in energy input
- [Biefeld-Brown Effect](#): “an ionic wind that transfers its momentum to surrounding neutral particles”
- [Static Electricity](#): “a stationary electric charge, typically produced by friction, which causes sparks or crackling or the attraction of dust or hair.”
- [Ball Lightning](#): “a rare and little known kind of lightning having the form of a moving globe of light several centimeters across which persists for periods of up to a minute.”
- [Plasma behavior](#) ([many](#)): the primary mode of matter (98% of known matter), aka [the “4th state”](#)
- [Photoelectric Effect](#): “the emission of electrons or other free carriers when light hits a material”
- [Hysteresis](#): “lagging of the magnetization of a [ferromagnetic](#) material, such as iron, behind variations of the magnetizing field”
- [Thermodynamics](#): 5 laws governing transfer of heat-energy between materials and systems (various)
- [Special Relativity](#): a subset of [Poincare's dynamics of the electron](#) based in [Lorentzian transformation of Maxwell](#); later described by Einstein in relation to the [previously discovered energy-mass relationship](#)
- [Dielectricity](#), [Dimagnetism](#), [Paramagnetism](#)
- [Scalar waves](#): EMF containing no vector dimension (not yet discovered); [CIA brief](#); [Are they possible?](#)

Magnetohydrodynamics

One sub-branch of study invented by [Nobel prize winner \(1970\) Hannes Alfvén](#) is the field of [MHD](#), a method of looking at magnetic fields as fluids, with their [inherent properties “frozen in.”](#) He also pioneered the ideas of [Alfvén waves](#) and [magnetic reconnection](#), but later [recanted this in favor of plasma-electric currents in space](#)^{1,2}. Nevertheless he has several important papers [here](#), [here](#), [here](#), and [here](#). He also initiated a new form of EM cosmology in the formation of planets and stars. Videos explaining this are found [here](#) and [here](#).

Quantum Electrodynamics and Chromodynamics

[QED](#) was invented as a way to deal with particle and subatomic particle energetic exchanges. [Richard Feynman](#) was most credited, but it included many people in the Quantum studies. Later, after [Murray Gell-Mann](#) et al. introduced [quarks](#), [QCD](#) was created to describe strong force interactions ([gluons](#)) using “color”.

Plasma Physics

The origins of [plasma physics](#) are in [spectroscopy](#) (since 1848) and the aurora work of [Kristian Birkeland](#), the first to postulate the [electric currents coming from the sun to affect the Earth’s atmosphere](#). Later this was confirmed with the discovery of the [Van Allen belts \(and more\)](#). The other pioneers in the early days included [Irving Langmuir](#) who invented a [probe to measure plasma](#), [Winston Bostick](#) who coined the term ‘[plasmoids](#)’ in 1957 and [1958](#), and [Ralph Jeurgens](#) who improved upon the Alfvén-Bostick plasma star concept into an [electric star](#) based on Melvin Cook’s [monograph](#) (1958) and [Velikovsky’s “Cosmos without Gravitation”](#) (1946).

Plasmoids

A [plasmoid](#)³ is an energetic self-sustaining EM entity which retains shape even after the removal of magnetic fields, as the ionization allows electricity and hysteresis to continue on in the entity. They often form what are called [plasma sheaths](#)⁴ or [double layers](#)⁵ which can grow, stretch, and even self-repair. In 2019 NASA released a [famous image of a plasmoid, M87](#) mislabeling it as a gravitic Black Hole⁶ (1967). However a study of the [BH model](#) used reveals it to be a form of [Marklund Convection](#). Furthermore counter-rotation in MHD ‘jets’ (BC’s) was already observed.⁷ Energetic currents have been measured [emerging from black holes](#) and [Active Galactic Nuclei](#) (and [quasars](#)), whose measured parameters are from [10¹⁵-10¹⁸ A](#).

¹ “In order to understand the phenomena in a certain plasma region, it is necessary to map not only the magnetic but also the electric field and the electric currents. Space is filled with a network of currents which transfer energy and momentum over large or very large distances. The currents often pinch to filamentary or surface currents. The latter are likely to give space, as also interstellar and intergalactic space, a cellular structure” ~1973

² <http://www.catastrophism.com/texts/electricity-in-space/>

³ “The plasma is emitted not as an amorphous blob, but in the form of a torus. We shall take the liberty of calling this toroidal structure a plasmoid, a word which means plasma-magnetic entity. The word **plasmoid** will be employed as a generic term for all plasma-magnetic entities,” W. Bostick, 1956

⁴ <https://people.eecs.berkeley.edu/~lieber/LiebermanGEC05rev.pdf>

⁵ <http://www.physics.ucla.edu/plasma-exp/research/BasicWaves&Instabilities/DoubleLayers/index.html>

⁶ http://www.chandra.harvard.edu/photo/2019/black_hole/

⁷ <http://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/2041-8205/788/1/L19/pdf>

Unified Aether Theory

The [Aether](#) has defied direct detection. The [Michelson-Morley experiment](#) gives [one result in horizontal rotation](#), and [another in vertical rotation](#). Physics has been divided between an aether known as [space-time](#) and another known as [quantum foam](#) ([strings](#), essentially), and another known as [Dark Matter](#) (and [Dark Energy](#)). Nevertheless, the only confirmed 'aether' yet found is [a massive supply](#) of [baryonic plasma](#) known as 'cosmic dust' or stellar 'wind.' In a UAT, the Force changes masses dependent on [charge density](#) (in agreement with particle physics), rather than [Newtonian inertia](#).

However, most [electro-gravitic theories](#) at this time rely on an as yet unproven [luminiferous](#) or fluidic aether and possibly ethons or [gravitons](#) what have you, to explain their method of transfer of interaction. The strongest proof for the aether remains the ordered/predictable Universe, which in 2019 was [proven to exist even on quantum scales](#). This may allow for 'spooky action at a distance' and other [entanglement](#) related issues via some aetheric energy transfer! But the disagreement in cosmology does not appear to be heading towards rectification any time soon. [Stephen Crothers' hilarious deconstructions](#) of [space-time](#) are supplemented by [NASA scientist Edward Dowdye](#)⁸ and physio-engineer [Wal Thornhill](#). This author's conjecture based upon [Cosmic Rearrangement hypothesis is that the aether is the "sea of charge."](#) and the 'spongy'⁹ [counterspace](#)¹⁰ (typically called Void but is not void; also called [vacuum energy or zero point](#)).

Birkeland Currents in a force-free model

Retired professor emeritus and [electrical engineer Donald Scott](#) improved upon the Alfven-Jeurgens model by releasing a) his own version of the [Electric Star model](#) and b) a Bessel function derived formula for [force-free Birkeland Currents](#) which decay at $r^{-1/2}$ rather than r^{-2} .

Marklund Convection and Z-pinching

Visually Marklund's convection demonstrates the coiling of Birkeland's currents, [the twisting of Alfven's MHD "flux ropes"](#), and the compression of Bostick's plasmoids. Importantly, too, they can (if conditions are right) result in [Bennet \(Z\) pinching](#) which may be implicated in the [formation of stars and planets](#). [Visual demonstration](#) is probably the best way to understand this complex process.

Structured Atomic Model

Edwin Kaal et al. released a [new form of atomic nucleus based upon platonic solids](#). For it to work, they rely upon eliminating the concept of neutrons (except as a placeholder model) in favor of small orbits of positive particles (positron) and electrons, which are then able to attract to their neighbors in predictable formations. This model has the favorable possibility of explaining disparate behaviors in isotopes, as well as strange alloying such as [Michigan copper's infusion with silver](#) (same family, just below it in [the periodic table](#)). It also may yield predictions regarding [plasma fusor "fusion"](#), [cold fusion](#), and electric arc radiation sequestration and transmutation of material.

⁸ https://www.theepochtimes.com/former-nasa-physicist-disputes-einsteins-relativity-theory_739183.html

⁹ I.e, absorbent space

¹⁰ <http://www.energeticforum.com/eric-dollard-official-forum/20244-space-counter-space-electricity-di-electricity.html>

Intrinsic Redshift

[Halton Arp](#) was a student of the famous [Edwin Hubble](#), and has hundreds of galaxies named after him. Nevertheless when he released [information regarding drastic redshift gulfs](#) between parent galaxies and their obviously (visually confirmed¹¹) connected child-quasars that had been ejected (perhaps through [lattice exclusion](#)), he was [blackballed and refused telescope time](#). He introduced formula along with his visual evidence for [intrinsic redshift](#). In [2018 data was released](#) from [GAIA DR2](#) which showed that ground based telescope distance measurements had been off by several orders of magnitude.

Nevertheless doppler redshift theory remains the single linchpin upholding the Big Bang hypothesis, which was introduced the same year as Plasma Cosmology (1927), but had the favor of the most famous scientist in history, Albert Einstein.¹² [Despite the visual evidence](#), Dark Energy remains a staple hypothesis (with no hard evidence) in the SM. And this is despite the evidence presented by professor Pier-Marrie Robitaille et al. that the [cosmic background radiation](#) is a measurement of the [Ocean's black-body radiation](#), and [atmospheric interference](#)¹³. It may be interesting to note that [Bostick predicted cosmic expansion](#) without a "[cosmological constant](#)" by analyzing plasmoid expansion in **laboratory experiments**.

Condensed Matter and Liquid Metallic Hydrogen

Robitaille et al. utilize [condensed matter](#) and [LMH physics](#), and [disproved Kirchoff's \(unproven\) "Law"](#) to explain the sun's physical and optical behaviors. While the [LMH predicts a neutral surface](#), the surface has granular behavior as well as [vortitional behavior](#), the [LMH hypothesis](#) has been utilized in discussing [Jupiter and Saturn's cores](#). [Lattice exclusion provides a potential source](#) for satellite birth and expulsion. It may be an alternative or addendum to the Thornhill-Scott hypothesis for the Venus ejection hypothesis regarding the **recorded worldwide** birth of Venus¹⁴ 5-6kya. [A hybridized model](#) may also explain unique solar system arrangements such as the [TRAPPIST-1 system](#), which can definitely be said to be impossible under an accretion (gravitic) model. It might also account for neutron star/pulsar/magnetar behaviors, which [Scott has described as "transistor like."](#) Matter fusion due to anode-only charge accumulation might augment the LMH hypothesis to provide forceful impetus for lattice exclusion. As of yet the two models remain separate.

Electrokinetics

[Electrokinetics](#) describes the famous effects that many ascribe to aether influence, or the Earth's own magnetosphere, which can give lift, thrust, or repulsion by utilizing charge. Some effects have been confirmed, and some are merely visual. It has been [hypothesized that the Stealth B-2 bomber uses these effects](#) (T. Valone). It is also likely that the [Voyager and Pioneer drifts](#) are due to this effect in the presence of the Solar Wind, rather than the irrational photonic bombardment/momentum concept (given photons, $m=0$, [are a model only and not real particles](#)).

¹¹ Herbig-Haro objects "are bright patches of nebulosity associated with newborn stars. They are formed when narrow jets of partially ionized gas ejected by said stars collide with nearby clouds of gas and dust at speeds of several hundred kilometers per second." https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Herbig%E2%80%93Haro_object

¹² However not all agree(d) with General Relativity which has yet to produce a single example of pure macrolensing > R1, and which was not challenged by Henri Poincare (creator of gravity waves and relativity theory) on account of Poincare's death in 1912.

¹³ The CMB signal disappears using the tilted Herouni [radioscope](#). <http://rnas.asj-oa.am/2542/1/73.pdf>

¹⁴ [Readings in Classical Nahuatl: The Death of Quetzalcoatl](#)

Electrogravitics

This describes the suspicion since Newton and Gilbert through to Franklin, Faraday, and Maxwell [to now that the gravity model is a special subset](#) of electrical behavior. Thornhill describes gravity as the effect that remains once a system has discharged the currents into the formation of matter, and it takes over as an attractive force because it is as Alfvén described, “the ashes of electrical behaviors.” Nevertheless, while the model has a prediction based upon charge separations, it remains true that neutrons obey gravity despite being electrically neutral. At this time, EG remains the major obstacle to Force unification. Certainly gravity is far too weak¹⁵ to describe cosmic interaction (and this is already known/implicit). Gareth Samuel has described this author’s Cosmic Rearrangement concept in [this video detailing how the local Void relationship to expansion defies the SM](#).

Stellar Physics and Fusion (brief)

One of the key differences between EPEMC and SM is that while the SM continues to assume a hot gaseous gravitic-collapse form of fusion in the sun and stars, for which they have multiple lines of reasoning [which simply cannot exist](#), the various alternate cosmologies seeking answers based their hypotheses upon lab and cosmic evidence, as well as philosophical reasoning based on simple observations in Nature¹⁶. The SM relies upon antiquated concepts that were [invented prior to the atomic era](#), as well as mathematics that make grand leaps of assumptions about the interior of the sun (which we cannot and have never measured directly).

However, accurate atomic physics all involve **lab-based observations**, with math being a tool for understanding the evidence, as [explained by Dr. Feynman](#)¹⁷. This fundamental misunderstanding has led to failures in stellar fusion models to predict solar cycle behavior such as transistor-like behaviors, as well as numerous misunderstandings of the solar system dynamics and baseless predictions, as well as a misunderstanding until recently as to the Earth’s magnetospheric dynamical relationship due to [spatial geocurrents](#).

¹⁵ Literally 10^{38} x weaker than EMF

¹⁶ Such as this author’s description of the [Laws of Energy and Laws of Life](#) (see Appendices)

¹⁷ Also: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hxKw4xEEFHQ>

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